

ORIGINAL PAPER

No beneficial effect of isopathic prophylactic treatment for birch pollen allergy during a low-pollen season: a double-blind, placebo-controlled clinical trial of homeopathic *Betula 30c*

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The objective of this research was to determine if the homeopathic medicine *Betula 30c* is more effective than placebo at reducing symptoms of pollen allergy in patients sensitive to birch pollen. It was a double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled trial. Tablets were given both as a prophylactic agent, once a week four weeks before the pollen season and as an acute remedy during the pollen season. The study was done in Oslo, Norway, in May 1996 and involved 73 children, adolescents and young adults from 7 to 25 y of age. Allergy-symptoms were assessed on a visual analogue scale (VAS) by patients or parents. Main outcome measure was the median (with its 95% confidence interval) of the symptom scores for all the treated patients, each day during a 10-day period. The pollen count was very low in 1996, only three days were high enough to provoke allergic symptoms. Surprisingly, the verum treated patients fared worse than the placebo group; they used more rescue medication and had higher symptom scores during these three days. Homeopaths might attribute the findings to a putative aggravation response, but the results certainly do not lend support to the usefulness of the tested prophylactic approach, under conditions of low allergen exposure. *British Homeopathic Journal* (2000) 89, 169–173.

Keywords: *Betula 30c*; birch pollen allergy; hay fever; homeopathy; isopathy

Introduction

The 'jury is still out', concerning the possible therapeutic effects of homeopathy, as reflected by headlines like 'Effectiveness of homeopathy, an endless story'.¹ In spite of Linde *et al*'s recent contribution² where they refuted the placebo hypothesis, the critics still deny any direct and real therapeutic effect of homeopathic remedies, because 'the infinite dilutions cannot possibly produce any effect',³ or because the 'rational basis for homeopathy is lacking'.⁴ Nevertheless, millions of people have tried homeopathic remedies and claim that they obtain satisfactory relief for their complaints.⁵ Even the deans of medical

schools in Britain and the United States want to introduce homeopathy in their curricula.^{6,7}

We performed a double-blind placebo-controlled study of a highly diluted preparation of pollen from birch trees (*Betula 30c*, this method is called homeopathic immunotherapy) to patients with birch pollen allergy (Aabel *et al* this issue).⁸ The results showed relief of symptoms in the *Betula* group that was not seen in the placebo group. However, some patients reported aggravation of symptoms, possibly due to the tablets, more often in the verum than in the placebo group. Since the remedy might have such adverse effects, the present study used a different design concerning instructions for use of tablets.

Homeopaths claim that their remedies work better on children and young adults than on older subjects, so we decided to include patients in age group 7–25.

Isopathy is a form of standardized homeopathic therapy, in which the medication is not individualized,

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but all patients receive the same medicine and dosage. In this study, where a diluted and succussed solution of the causative allergen was used,⁹ we refer to it as homeopathic immunotherapy. The usual way of giving these remedies has been at low potencies, such as 6× or 12× (a dilution of the original allergen solution to 1/10⁶ and 1/10¹², respectively) several times a day. In pollen allergy the remedies are often administered prophylactically before the season starts.¹⁰ We decided to use a higher dilution to be sure that practically no allergen could be left in the medicine solution used, thereby removing any similarity to conventional immunotherapy.¹¹

The aim of this study was thus to investigate whether the homeopathic remedy *Betula* 30c could reduce symptoms more than a placebo preparation, both as a prophylactic agent and as an acute treatment during the pollen season. Furthermore, we would clarify whether this schedule—including a stricter instruction not to overdose the remedy—could minimize the problem of aggravation.

Patients and methods

Recruitment and patient selection

One hundred and forty patients were recruited through a newspaper article in March 1996. They all lived in the Oslo area and were given a clinical interview by the author regarding their allergy and general health. Children were interviewed with their parents.

Participants were required to have a clear history of birch pollen allergy and a positive skin prick test for birch. Those who had a test done in the previous two years had to bring the results with them to the interview, and those who did not had to order a new one by their own GP before entering the study.

Eighty patients of both sexes, 7–25 y of age, were included. Excluded were patients with diseases of any kind other than the above-mentioned allergy (including those suffering from eczema and asthma) and conditions causing nasal obstruction (like polyps, septum deviation and chronic edema due to perennial rhinitis, etc). This information was given by the patients or their parents during the clinical interview. Excluded were also patients using medication of and kind (including oral contraceptives), women pregnant or actively seeking pregnancy, lactating mothers, and finally those not willing to stop drinking coca-cola or coffee or both during the treatment period. This last requirement was because of a possible interference of these drinks with homeopathic treatment.¹²

Trial design

The study was designed as a double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. Each patient received a tablet vial randomly coded with a number, in such a way that half of the patients would receive placebo and the other half *Betula* 30c. The instruction for tablet use

was: 'one tablet *once* a week for 4 weeks, thereafter one tablet when you get allergy symptoms. Wait 12 hours before taking the next. Resume tablet intake if symptoms return. If very high levels of pollen occur, you may take up to three tablets a day.' The patients were instructed to abstain from coffee and coca-cola (to avoid caffeine intake) for at least three weeks before entering the study. They should also as far as possible avoid operations (including dental treatments), vaccination and exposure to camphor, peppermint and menthol, as these factors are believed by homeopaths to interfere with their medicines.¹² They were allowed to take local antihistamines (nasal spray and eye drops), and if the allergy symptoms were very bad, they could also use systemic antihistamines and antiasthmatics (including steroid spray).

Study diaries

The patients were instructed how to complete registration forms. All patients were asked to complete a diary for 10 days, each day marking allergy symptoms on a visual analogue scale. (VAS, a 10-cm line where 'no complaints' is at one end and 'maximum complaints' at the other end). VAS was preferred instead of sum score, as used at our previous trial, because this method is considered to be more valid for evaluation of hay fever.¹³ During the prophylactic period no diary was kept. The 10-day diary started on the day when symptoms first occurred and for asymptomatic subjects day 1 was when the first pollen count was reported on the radio or TV. In other words, the opening days of the symptomatic period were taken as baseline. Patients were also asked to record the number of experimental tablets taken, as well as the use of rescue medication (conventional anti-allergy treatment) each day.

Drug preparation

The tablets used in our trial were produced by Drogecentralen Göteborg (DCG), Sweden, according to GMP (Good Manufacturing Practice).¹⁴ Briefly, tablets are sucrose globules, the basis for most homeopathic remedies, which are impregnated with a succussed and diluted solution. In a clinical trial, these sucrose globules can be used as placebo tablets because they are identical to the homeopathic ones with respect to colour, size, shape, taste and weight. The homeopathic tablets were impregnated with a solution of *Betula alba* 30c. This solution was made from a birch pollen extract diluted and succussed according to strict procedures 1 : 99 thirty times. The impregnation was done three times. For practical purposes, we decided to use plain sucrose globules as placebo, ie they were not impregnated with succussed diluent. The vials were sent to a statistician for random coding (only a number on each vial) and then distributed to the participating patients by the author.

Pollen counts and weather

Pollen is regularly counted in the Oslo air during the flowering season. 1996 was an unusual year because the production of pollen was very poor. In addition, it was cold and wet so the spread of pollen was very low. On three days, 12, 13 and 14 May, the temperature rose and the pollen count was sufficient to give symptoms (Figure 2).

Statistics

A power calculation showed that 80 patients were required to detect a difference between groups of 1.5cm in pooled symptom sum score on the VAS, given an assumed standard deviation of 2. This difference was considered clinically relevant.¹³ A 5% significance level and a statistical power of 90% was chosen. The daily allergy symptom scores from days 1 to 10 were collected for all the subjects, giving rise to point estimates for the test and placebo groups. As main outcome measure we had chosen the median VAS with its 95% confidence interval (CI). A two-sided Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney two-sample test was used to compare the test and placebo groups. Chi-square testing compared the frequency of persons with symptoms above and below 2.5cm (ie 25% of the total VAS, which had been chosen beforehand as a cut-off point between high and low scores) on the critical days. This test also assessed the use of rescue medication in the two groups. All statistical analyses were performed before the treatment code was broken.

Ethics

Informed and written consent was obtained from all patients. The study was part of a research program on unconventional medicine under the Research Council of Norway and was approved by the Regional Ethics Committee for Medical Research and also by the Homoeopathic Ethical Committee.

Results

Patient characteristics. Allergen exposure

Among 140 people willing to participate, 60 were excluded according to the selection criteria and 80 entered the study. Two patients misunderstood the instructions and did not adhere to the tablet dosage schedule, nor did they report their symptoms. Five patients did not return the registration forms and did not answer the reminder. Consequently, 73 patients completed the study, 36 in the placebo group and 37 in the *Betula* group (Figure 1). The treatment groups were comparable with respect to age, sex, years with allergy, degree of allergy—but differed in their previous experience with unconventional medicine (Table 1).

Data concerning pollen counts and air temperatures are shown in Figure 2, lower panel. This year was

Figure 1 Consort flow diagram showing numbers recruited, excluded, randomized, drop-outs and individuals included in the final analysis.

exceptional concerning pollen spread and weather in many ways: first, the first day birch pollen was detected was the 9 May, whereas the average from many years of observation is the 1 May; second, the weather was very cold and wet during the period; and third, the temperature rose suddenly on the 12 May (Figure 2).

Symptom course

The symptom course for the two groups is shown in Figure 2, upper panel. The differences between groups with their 95% CI are given in the panel below. (Note that the point estimates will not equal the differences between medians.) On the critical days 12, 13, and 14 May, the treatment favoured the placebo group, which had lower symptom scores. The maximum difference was found on 14 May, namely 1.3 (−0.1—2.5, 95% CI; $P=0.08$). We also calculated the difference in another way (see Statistics above), with the value 2.5 as a cut-off point. Then 19 persons had a higher score than 2.5 in the *Betula* group and only 10 persons in the placebo group ($P=0.03$). There was no significant difference between the groups with respect to start of symptoms; 9 May was the average date for both groups. Accordingly, there was no difference between the groups with respect to mean number of days from zero symptoms to appearance of first symptoms.

Discussion

Prophylactic allergy treatment with *Betula* 30c surprisingly led to higher symptom scores than placebo. In addition, even though not statistically significant, the *Betula* group used more rescue medication than the placebo group—which suggests that their symptom scores without this intervention would have been even higher. The groups were randomized to the two treatments; nevertheless, there were more people in the *Betula* group who had tried unconventional treatment before, and therefore had a positive attitude to the study. Presumably, these subjects would anticipate a positive treatment effect, giving at least a high placebo response. This was apparently not the case.

A statistical type 1 error, ie rejection of a null hypothesis even if it was true could explain the findings. However, interpreting the results as not significant ($P=0.08$ in an alternative analytic approach, see Results section), would open the possibility of a type 2 error, ie accepting the null hypothesis even if it was false, due to a too small number of patients.

We did not find any difference between groups with respect to the first day of symptoms. If the *Betula* tablets had worked prophylactically, one would expect symptoms to appear later in the test than in the control group and also that the test subjects had fewer symptoms. Therefore, under the pollen conditions in 1996 in Oslo, the conclusion must be that the prophylactic treatment with the isopathic remedy *Betula* 30c was not effective. Apparently *Betula* tablets provoked a negative effect in some patients. This phenomenon has been described in several other studies of homeopathy and is also a well-known term in the homeopathic philosophy.^{12,15,16} The finding could certainly lead to speculations whether *Betula* 30c somehow was too potent, aggravating symptoms in certain sensitive individuals. Correction of the dose, either with fewer tablets or with a lower potency of each tablet would then have been appropriate.

The study turned out to be atypical concerning the allergen exposure. In a way, our study was very similar to a standardized laboratory situation. A very cold May, delayed start of pollen spread and then suddenly 3 days with high pollen count and then reversion to 'baseline' with cold, wet weather and low pollen count. However, the pollen exposure was certainly suboptimal for provocation of allergic symptoms (Figure 2). It is therefore unclear what would have happened to the test and control groups under more usual pollen conditions or later in May, because the symptom reporting period was only 10 days. In Reilly *et al*'s first study of hay fever with isopathy the beneficial effect appeared as late as 18 days after start of medication.¹⁵ Therefore, the study should be repeated in a more normal pollen year, preferably as a pure prophylactic trial of longer duration. During the pollen season patients could then use their ordinary medication.

Figure 2 Overview of symptom scores and atmospheric conditions. The upper panel gives symptom course for the two groups in the pollen season, with number of patients participating. The middle panel shows the difference in median symptom score between the two groups, with point estimates and their 95% confidence intervals for each day. The two lower panels depict pollen counts each day during the period from 7 to 19 May and mean air temperature each day for the same period.

Compliance. Aggravation. Use of antihistamines

The diaries showed that all the patients had taken the remedy correctly. There was no difference between groups with respect to number of tablets taken during the 10-day period. There were no complaints about aggravation of symptoms. The use of rescue medication was minimal: in the *Betula* group 12 persons used 67 doses of rescue medication, and in the placebo group seven persons used 36 doses (one dose being equivalent to either one tablet of antihistamine or one dose of either nasal spray or eye drops) ($P=0.58$).

Neither the patients nor the primary investigator's opinion about what kind of tablets the patients had received—whether placebo or verum—differed appreciably between the groups.

Table 1 Baseline characteristics of patients treated with *Betula* 30c or placebo

	<i>Betula</i> 30c	Placebo
Age of patients (yr)*	12.8 (6–24)	11.7 (6–22)
Sex and number	19f, 18m	21f, 15m
Duration of allergy (yr)*	6 (1–20)	5 (1–12)
Symptoms day 1 [†]	2.0 (2.2)	1.7 (2.0)
Prior UT [‡]	14	6

*Means with ranges in parentheses.

[†]Mean symptom score (VAS) with standard deviation in parentheses.

[‡]Number of subjects who had tried unconventional treatment (UT) before this study.

In any case, this study does not support recommendation of *Betula* 30c as a preventive treatment for birch pollen allergy under conditions with low allergen exposure and administered as in the present study.

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